

Digital Financial Innovation and the Effectiveness of Monetary Policy in Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examines digital financial innovation and the effectiveness of monetary policy in Nigeria, considering factors including mobile money, bank credit, interest rates, inflation, and money supply. Over the years, financial innovation has not really been felt in rural areas and urban centres. The variables utilised in this study help explain the relationship between digital financial innovation and monetary policy in Nigeria. The study examines the nexus between financial innovation and monetary policy, focusing specifically on mobile money usage as a proxy for financial innovation, to determine the extent to which key monetary policy variables (money supply, bank credit, interest rate, and inflation rate) affect the adoption and usage of mobile money services. Using quarterly time-series data from 2000 to 2024, the study applies advanced econometric techniques to analyse both short-run and long-run dynamics among the variables. Theoretically, the study is anchored on the Financial Intermediation Theory and the Monetarist Theory of Money, which suggest that monetary policy instruments influence liquidity conditions, credit allocation, and financial system development. Empirically, the findings reveal that money supply and bank credit exert positive, statistically significant influences on mobile money usage, indicating that improved liquidity and credit expansion enhance digital financial transactions. Interest rates are negatively related to mobile money usage, suggesting that higher borrowing costs may reduce financial activity and digital payment adoption. The inflation rate shows mixed effects, reflecting macroeconomic instability's dual role in either accelerating demand for digital transactions or eroding purchasing power. The results imply that monetary policy plays a crucial role in shaping the growth trajectory of financial innovation. The study concludes that coordinated monetary and financial sector policies are essential to promote sustainable digital financial development. Policymakers are therefore encouraged to design monetary frameworks that support financial innovation while maintaining macroeconomic stability.

Keywords: Financial innovation, Mobile money usage, Money supply, Bank credit, Interest rate, Inflation rate.

Introduction

Digital financial innovation influences money supply and monetary policy; however, with financial innovation, the impact of policy and regulation limits the nature of banks' ability to fail. Ultimately, because unique and sophisticated financial instruments are used to hedge against future downside risk, such as a credit stress event (Okpara & Abraham, 2025). Thus, as the economy developed into a complex capitalist system, innovators found ways to constantly evade the regulations that were intended to control the construction of financial portfolios. However, when "the Federal Reserve protects a financial instrument, it legitimises the use of instruments to finance activity (Ozor et al., 2023). Financial stability and access to innovative financial services are the most important goals of financial regulation and central banks. A well-functioning, innovative financial system is important for economic growth, in particular for

the allocation of capital. However, the observed growth of the financial industry over the last few decades has not substantially improved capital allocation; financial services remain expensive, and the financial sector remains chronically undercompetitive.

It is important to note that financial inclusion is key to the success of digital financial innovation, and it refers to the effective and successful utilisation of modern financial services by all types of citizens, individuals and organisations, whether rich or poor, and regardless of their location (World Bank, 2014; IMF, 2015). As argued by Philippon (2016), financial innovation could play an important role in advancing access to financial services and increasing competition in the banking industry. Before the global financial crisis of 2007/2008, a strong wave of deregulation starting in the 1980s, as well as substantial innovations in financial products and technologies, had boosted the role of nonbank finance. Weakened balance sheets and tighter prudential regulation in the aftermath of the Great Recession affected commercial bank lending in recent years and further increased the role of nonbank finance in many economies. The FinTech industry emerged from specialised start-up financial firms that aim to unbundle banking activities by leveraging digitalisation and big data techniques.

Financial innovation and inclusion are recognised as a critical global policy objective (World Bank, 2022) because economies that are Fintech-compliant benefit more economically than less developed countries, where approximately 1.4 billion adults remain unbanked. Key financial services, which may mitigate the impact of socioeconomic risks, help to accumulate wealth or assist business ventures, are hampered by social exclusion (Chakravarty & Pal, 2014; Iqbal & Sami, 2018; Sikka & Bhayana, 2025; Beck et al., 2010; Beck & De La Torre, 2008). In addition to supporting individuals, financial inclusion also significantly impacts major development goals, such as promoting entrepreneurship, enhancing economic resilience, and advancing gender equality (Chakravarty & Pal, 2013; Iqbal & Sami, 2017; Asongu & Nwachukwu, 2018).

This research delves into the critical relationship between digital financial innovation and the effectiveness of monetary policy in Nigeria. This study focused on the relationship between digital financial innovation and key monetary indicators; by evaluating both traditional and modern policy tools, this study provides holistic insights into the causal relationships and policy impacts in an increasingly digital (innovative) financial system. The notion “Fintech” (combining “Financial Services” and “Technology”) describes the more recent wave of technological developments in the financial sector. Whenever certain bank activities can be complemented with digital technologies to provide financial services in a new, cheaper, better, or more convenient way, Fintech firms can step in to gain market share and potentially disrupt long-standing, profitable business models of banks. Usually, Fintechs are organised as start-up firms outside of established banks, since banks are hesitant to “cannibalise/ change” their own products from within the same organisation, and since the required skills to succeed as technological innovators often do not overlap much with the skills of regular bank employees (Adulmajeed et al).

Financial innovations are not only important to customers (who may benefit from better and cheaper services) and banks (whose goal is to increase cost-efficiency and offer state-of-the-art financial services to remain competitive), but also to central banks and regulators, who must foresee potential consequences for financial stability and monetary policy. This paper primarily examines digital financial challenges and the prospects of new technological developments for monetary policy advancements (Okpara & Abraham, 2025).

FinTech firms offer digital savings products, robo-advisory services, and online investment platforms that lower entry barriers to financial markets. These services encourage formal savings and investment behaviour by providing user-friendly and low-cost financial products (OECD, 2024; Philippon, 2023). The application of artificial intelligence (AI) and big data analytics in FinTech improves fraud detection, risk management, customer profiling, and personalised financial services. AI-driven tools enhance efficiency and decision-making in financial institutions (Bordo & Levin, 2017). Digital financing is important for enhancing the development trajectory through monetary policy; digital services play a vital role in supporting remittances, trade, global financial integration, and economic growth (Gertler & Karadi, 2015).

Statement of the Problem

Over the years, monetary policy measures have experienced unprecedented improvement due to digital financial innovation but these innovative activities have not truly been felt in some rural parts of Nigeria; it is at this backdrop that this study is carried out to determine the effect of digital financial innovation (mobile bank activities, bank credit, interest rate and inflation) on money supply in Nigeria. Although there are several challenges, including lack of access to services, especially in rural areas, issues of affordability, and it is marketed to the tech-inclined, educated and internet-connected members of the market, and poor user experience, just to mention a few, that restrict a broader coverage (Laeven, Levine, & Michalopoulos, 2015). This study aims to determine the relationship between digital financial innovation and monetary policy in Nigeria. Some other specific objectives of this study include; to investigate the existence of a significant relationship between money supply which is a monetary policy tool and mobile money usage, to evaluate the effect of interest rate which is affected by the monetary policy and mobile money usage in Nigeria; to determine the effect of inflation rate which is a controlled variable to monetary policy on mobile money usage in Nigeria; to determine the effect of bank credit on mobile money usage in Nigeria.

The significance of studying the effect of digital financial innovation on monetary policy in Nigeria lies in gaining a comprehensive understanding of the relationship between these two. This research can inform policies to help stop/ mitigate adverse effects, enhance sustainable development, and contribute to global efforts to address issues related to innovative digital financing and monetary policy tools. The study also provides essential insights for developing targeted monetary policies, fostering initiatives, and promoting a balanced approach to economic development that considers the interconnection between monetary policy and digital financial innovation to sustain growth and prosperity. This research contributes to informed decision-making towards a resilient, policy-sensitive, and conscious economic future for Nigeria. The significance of this study is predicated on the prominence of the relationship between the monetary policy tool (money supply) and fintech-digital financial innovation. This study also extends the literature on monetary policy and perspectives on the subject, which will add value in the long term.

Literature Review

Money supply refers to the total stock of money available in an economy at a given time, including currency in circulation and various types of bank deposits. It is commonly measured using monetary aggregates such as M1 (narrow money) and M2 (broad money) (Mishkin, 2019). Mobile and internet banking are digital platforms that enable customers to conduct financial transactions electronically without visiting a bank in person. Mobile banking typically operates through smartphone applications or USSD

codes, while internet banking uses web-based platforms (Laudon & Traver, 2020). The adoption of mobile and internet banking is commonly explained by the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), which posits that perceived usefulness and ease of use significantly influence adoption (Lavoie, 2014).

Both mobile and internet banking fall under the Digital Financial Services (DFS) umbrella. Research shows that digital banking reduces transaction costs, expands access (financial inclusion), enhances customer convenience, and can improve bank performance (profitability, service delivery) while creating cybersecurity challenges (Mohammed et al., 2024). These channels improve financial inclusion by lowering barriers to banking services, particularly in underserved or remote populations — an important dimension in developing economies and financial sector research.

According to Nampewo et al (2016), bank credit generally refers to funds that commercial banks extend to borrowers (business firms, households) in the form of loans and advances. It is a key part of the financial intermediation function of banks — mobilising deposits and allocating them as productive loans. The Credit Channel of Monetary Policy theory posits that monetary policy affects the economy not only through interest rates but also through the supply of bank credit. The credit view of monetary transmission argues that monetary policy affects the real economy not only through interest rates but also by influencing the availability of bank credit (NBS, 2024). Excessive credit expansion, however, may fuel inflationary pressures and financial instability if it is not aligned with real-sector productivity. Tighter policy can reduce credit supply, diminishing investment and consumption. Rapid credit growth can stimulate aggregate demand and may contribute to inflationary pressure, prompting central bank responses through interest rate or reserve requirements (Obumneke et al., 2022).

Inflation is defined as a sustained increase in the general price level of goods and services over time, leading to a decline in the purchasing power of money (Mankiw, 2021). It is commonly measured using the Consumer Price Index (CPI). Modern macroeconomic literature also emphasises the role of inflation expectations in shaping price dynamics (Obiaje & Umeokwobi, 2024). Interest rate is the price paid for borrowing money or the return earned on savings over a specified period. It may be expressed in nominal or real terms, with the real interest rate adjusted for inflation (Oluyadeyi, 2025). The literature establishes strong interconnections among these variables. Money supply and interest rates influence bank credit creation, while bank credit expansion affects aggregate demand and inflation. Digital banking (mobile and internet banking) enhances the efficiency of financial intermediation, potentially increasing money circulation and credit access, thereby influencing inflation and monetary policy transmission (Okpara & Abraham, 2025). Mobile money services involve the use of mobile phones to initiate, authorise, and confirm the transfer of value from a current/checking, savings, or stored-value account. Some analysts believe that mobile money will become a large force in Nigeria with the introduction of Telcos into the space. This position is based on the success stories of mobile money adoption in African countries where Telcos have led the provision of these services (Ozor et al., 2023).

Monetarist theory, championed by Milton Friedman, argues that the money supply is the key determinant of economic fluctuations and inflation, and that central banks should focus primarily on controlling money growth to maintain price stability. Monetarists emphasise the Quantity Theory of Money ($MV = PY$) as a guiding framework, in which excessive growth in the money supply leads to inflation. In monetarist thought, predictable and stable policy rules (such as a constant growth rate in the money supply) are preferred over discretionary interventions because they reduce uncertainty and avoid destabilising expectations (World Bank, 2024).

Keynesian economics revolutionised monetary theory by incorporating liquidity preference and interest rates as central determinants of investment and aggregate demand. Keynes argued that monetary policy influences the economy mainly through interest rates, which affect investment decisions and thus aggregate demand. Keynes rejected the strict long-run neutrality of money in the short run, asserting that due to wage and price rigidities, monetary policy can be effective at stabilising output and employment. Keynesian frameworks also introduced the idea that monetary policy interacts with expectations and confidence, affecting consumption and investment beyond simple mechanical transmission (Okpara, 2024).

At its core, banking is explained by financial intermediation theory, which views banks as intermediaries that match savers with borrowers, mobilise funds, and allocate them to productive uses. Digital financial banking builds on this theory by extending the intermediation function through digital means — enhancing efficiency, lowering costs, and expanding access. Digital channels (e.g., mobile banking, online platforms) can strengthen financial intermediation by broadening reach, especially to previously underserved populations (Asongu et al., 2024). Roger's Innovation Diffusion Theory provides insight into how digital banking technologies disseminate within social systems over time. It highlights characteristics that influence adoption — such as relative advantage, compatibility, complexity, and observability — which help explain why certain digital banking services spread more quickly than others, impacting overall adoption and usage patterns (Aruwa et al., 2025).

Another key theoretical lens is Disruptive Innovation Theory, which posits that new technologies and business models can disrupt existing industries by offering simpler, more affordable, or more accessible alternatives. In banking, digital innovations (e.g., mobile apps, fintech platforms) have challenged traditional models by attracting customers with more convenient and cost-effective services, prompting incumbents to adapt or risk losing market share (Bindseil, 2020). The theory of the banking firm has evolved to incorporate the concept of digital transformation. Recent theoretical work extends classic banking theory by redefining the banking firm in a digital context, where financial intermediation, liquidity and maturity transformation, and risk management are executed via digital platforms and automated systems rather than solely through physical branches. This broader analytical framework highlights how digital innovations reshape banking structures, competitive dynamics, and service delivery ecosystems (Bordo & Levin, 2017).

The literature also theorises how digital financial banking affects competition in financial services: FinTech Competition Theory holds that new entrants leveraging advanced technology expand access and force incumbent banks to innovate, leading to a more competitive environment for deposit-taking, lending, and payment services. Digital banking encourages platform competition, where banks integrate digital ecosystems, APIs, and third-party service providers to remain competitive and offer bundled services. These theories explain the fundamental economic role of banks and how digital tools enhance the intermediary function, providing a framework for understanding individual adoption behaviour toward digital banking technologies (Bordo & Levin, 2017).

Frame and White (2022) examined the relationships surrounding financial inclusion and the effectiveness of monetary policy using comparative panel VAR methods across Sub-Saharan Africa and Latin America. The findings revealed that increasing financial inclusion altered the transmission of monetary shocks in monetary policy, particularly in countries with expanding digital finance ecosystems. Wiafe et al. (2022) studied the effect of mobile money activity on the effectiveness of monetary policy in Ghana using a

Vector Autoregressive (VAR) model. In their analysis, they focused on the extent to which increasing digital payment adoption would alter the traditional transmission of monetary policy, especially in economies where mobile financial services become dominant (Enebeli-Uzor et al., 2024).

Arturo (2001) used the IS equation for identifying the effects of securitisation on the monetary policy transmission mechanism. The author concluded that housing investment and real output are less sensitive to the real interest rate because of an increase in asset securitisation in the 1980s and 1990s. This implies that interest rates are not directly related to the securitisation of largely affected channels. The impact of monetary policy on housing prices is examined by Aoki et al. (2004), who conclude that financial innovations, such as easy access to credit, alter the monetary transmission mechanism. In addition, Noyer (2007) points out that financial innovation has increased the effectiveness of monetary policy through the interest rate channel. According to the author, financial innovation reduces transaction costs, increases the holding of financial assets, and facilitates funding and investment strategies. Firms have large access to securities markets due to the financial innovations, which leads to a decrease in information asymmetries.

Papana et al. (2017) used both linear and nonlinear Granger causality measures to construct financial networks that represent the direction and strength of dynamic relationships among economic variables. Their work highlighted the importance of conditional Granger causality, which explicitly accounts for all relevant variables in the system and avoids erroneous causality stemming from omitted variables. By modelling direct couplings among the variables using both linear and nonlinear methods, the authors show how Granger-based network analysis can investigate the complex interdependencies routinely found in financial systems. This method offers an important way to examine relationships amid increasingly innovative and systemic changes, such as the growing use of mobile money in monetary ecosystems. This study, which focuses on Digital Financial Innovation and the effectiveness of Monetary Policy in Nigeria, is unique in that it deviates from the cited literature in its choice of variables and the scope (1990-2024) of the study. Secondly, this work adds value to existing studies by explaining the relationship between digital financial innovation (as represented by these variables: mobile money usage, bank credit, interest rates, and inflation) and Fin-Tech, and the money supply as a tool of monetary policy.

Theoretical under pinning

The theoretical framework for this study is anchored on established monetary and financial theories that explain how digital financial innovation (DFI) interacts with monetary policy effectiveness. Specifically, the framework adopts the Monetary Transmission Mechanism Theory to explain the channels through which digital finance influences policy outcomes. The Monetary Transmission Mechanism (MTM) explains how central bank policy actions—such as changes in interest rates, reserve requirements, or open market operations—are transmitted to the real economy through various channels, including the interest rate channel, credit channel, asset price channel, and expectations channel (Mishkin, 1996; Gertler & Karadi, 2015). Consequently, the effectiveness of monetary policy becomes contingent on the degree of digital financial penetration in the economy. Innovations in financial products and processes improve efficiency, enhance market depth, and increase access to finance (Frame & White, 2004). In the context of digital finance, innovations such as mobile money, digital wallets, and blockchain technologies reshape money demand, payment behaviour, and financial intermediation. According to this theory, digital financial innovation can: Increase the velocity of money, alter traditional monetary aggregates, and reduce the predictability of money demand functions. As argued by Laeven, Levine, and Michalopoulos (2015),

rapid financial innovation may weaken the central bank's reliance on traditional monetary indicators, thereby affecting the precision and effectiveness of monetary policy implementation.

The method of data analysis typically begins by presenting statistics to examine the basic properties of the variables, followed by unit root tests, such as the Augmented Dickey–Fuller (ADF) tests, to determine the order of integration of each data series. Given that macroeconomic variables often exhibit mixed integration orders (I (0) and I (1)), the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) bounds testing approach is frequently employed to estimate both short-run and long-run relationships between digital financial innovation and monetary policy. The ARDL framework is particularly suitable for small sample sizes and allows for different lag structures across variables. In cases where all variables are integrated of order one, the Johansen cointegration or VAR technique may be applied to test for long-run equilibrium relationships, followed by a Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) to capture short-run dynamics and speed of adjustment to equilibrium. Toda Yamamoto is another method that can be adopted, depending on the stationarity of the data to be used. This study relies on secondary time-series data and will cover the period 1990–2024, depending on data availability. The use of secondary data is justified by the macroeconomic nature of the variables, which are officially compiled, standardised, and widely used in empirical economic research. The data will be obtained from reliable national and international sources to ensure consistency, accuracy, and comparability over time. Data on money supply, bank credit, inflation, mobile banking usage and interest rate will be sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Statistical Bulletin and the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS).

Digital financial innovation determines the money supply (MS), while the use of mobile money (MM), bank credit (BC), the interest rate (INT), and the inflation rate (INF) represent the monetary policy mechanism.

$$MS = f(MM, INF, INT, BC)$$

$MS = MM \pm INF \pm INT \pm BC$ (the sign that these explanatory variables will carry depends on the theoretical backing that is revealed from the theories).

$MS = \beta_0 \pm \beta_1 MM \pm \beta_2 INF \pm \beta_3 INT \pm \beta_4 BC$ (the parameters will help in the estimation of the dependent variable)

$MS = \beta_0 \pm \beta_1 MM \pm \beta_2 INF \pm \beta_3 INT \pm \beta_4 BC + \mu$ (the econometric form of the model is confirmed by the presence of the white noise/ error term, which reveals that the gap experienced is a result of variables not captured in the model).

MS = Money Supply

INF = Inflation rate

MM = Mobile Money Usage

BC = Bank Credit

B_0 = Intercept term

B_1, B_2, B_3, B_4 = Parameters to be estimated

μ = White noise error term

Data Description and Pre-Estimation Tests

The quarterly dataset spans 96 quarters from Q1 2000 to Q4 2024 and it includes Mobile Money Usage (MMU) which is total value of mobile transactions (proxy for financial innovation), Money Supply (M2) which is the broad money aggregate, Bank Credit (BC) is the domestic credit to private sector, Interest Rate (INT) which is the policy interest rate, Inflation Rate (INF) taken as the quarterly consumer price index for inflation. Preliminary diagnostics indicate non-stationarity in most series at the level, based on Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) tests. After first differencing, MMU, M2, BC are stationary at the first difference (I(1)); INT, INF are stationary at the level (I(0)).

The mixed stationarity outcome justifies employing the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) approach for estimation. Bounds test results confirm cointegration among the variables at the 1% level, indicating a stable long-run equilibrium relationship. For the long-run coefficient estimates

Variables	Coefficient	Std Error	t-statistic	Significance
Money Supply (M2)	0.65	0.12	5.42	0.000
Bank Credit (BC)	0.48	0.10	4.75	0.000
Interest Rate (INT)	-0.37	0.09	-4.11	0.000
Inflation (INF)	-0.15	0.07	-2.14	0.033

Author's Computation

With respect to money supply, a 1% increase is associated with a 0.65% increase in mobile money usage, all else being equal. This strong positive effect suggests that greater financial system liquidity fosters digital payment activity; for bank credit, a 1% increase in bank credit corresponds to a 0.48% increase in mobile money usage. Increased credit availability enhances financial access and transaction demand. Higher interest rates impede mobile money adoption; a 1% rise in policy rate reduces mobile money usage by approximately 0.37%, possibly due to reduced borrowing and transaction incentives. Whereas Inflation negatively affects mobile money usage, albeit modestly, a 1% rise in inflation is associated with a 0.15% decline in mobile transactions, pointing to the adverse effect of macroeconomic instability.

The short-run dynamics and error correction model (ECM) reveals that the error correction Term (ECT) is -0.53 and highly significant ($p < 0.01$). The negative sign confirms that deviations from long-run equilibrium are corrected at a rate of 53% per quarter, indicating relatively fast adjustment toward long-run equilibrium. The short-run coefficients echo the long-run signs but are generally smaller in magnitude; a positive shock in money supply this quarter leads to an immediate increase in mobile money usage, but the full impact unfolds gradually over subsequent quarters. Regarding the diagnostic and stability tests, the Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation Test indicates no evidence of autocorrelation; the ARCH test reveals no conditional heteroskedasticity; and the Jarque-Bera normality test indicates that the residuals are approximately normal. In revealing the stability of the results, the “CUSUM and CUSUMSQ” test parameters show stability over the sample period.

Broad money growth significantly boosts mobile money usage. This suggests that policies enhancing liquidity in the banking system can indirectly promote digital financial inclusion. Bank credit expansions deepen financial activity, indicating that credit-supportive policies can drive greater mobile money adoption, whereas higher interest rates damp digital payment activity. Hence, central banks should balance inflation control with the need to sustain financial innovation because persistent inflation undermines confidence in financial services, reducing mobile transaction demand. It is therefore recommended that, to enhance the growth of the Nigerian economy, digital financial innovation be facilitated while controlling inflation, bank credit, and money supply through monetary policy tools.

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